

МАРКЕТИНГ

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**Application of SWOT-analysis in Branding and Marketing of TNCs in
the Global Clothing Market (based on the Materials of Zara, Nike, Dior,
Prada Companies)**

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***Abstract.** Purpose. The main goal of this study is to apply the SWOT analysis method to examine branding and marketing strategies of leading companies in the fashion and sports sectors (Nike, Zara, Dior, and Prada) for the period from 2020 to 2023. Methods. We used SWOT analysis to evaluate the branding and marketing activities of the studied companies, identifying their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This qualitative analysis allows for a comprehensive assessment of company branding and marketing, identifying their competitive advantages and disadvantages, and considering potential risks and development prospects. Results. The SWOT analysis enabled the assessment of internal and external factors affecting the competitive positions of the companies, as well as the identification of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats for each of them.*

The study showed that luxury and mass-market segments use different approaches to branding and marketing, but both segments actively leverage their brands to enhance competitiveness. Luxury brands such as Dior and Prada are associated with prestige and elegance, while mass-market brands like Nike and Zara ensure the accessibility of their products to a wide range of consumers. The main opportunities for all brands include expansion into new markets, development of environmental initiatives, and digital marketing. Conclusions. It is crucial for all brands to develop new markets, environmental initiatives, and digital marketing to enhance competitiveness. Threats for all companies include political and military conflicts leading to economic crises, as well as reputational risks. Opportunities for both segments include expansion into emerging markets, development of environmental initiatives, and ethical practices.

Keywords: *branding, marketing, SWOT-analysis, transnational multinational corporations.*

Застосування SWOT-аналізу при брендуванні та маркетингу ТНК на глобальному ринку одягу (на матеріалах компаній Zara, Nike, Dior, Prada)

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Анотація. *Мета. Основна мета даного дослідження полягає в*

застосуванні методу SWOT-аналізу щодо дослідження питання брендування та маркетингу для провідних компаній у сфері виробництва одягу (Nike, Zara, Dior та Prada) за період з 2020 по 2023 роки. Методи. Ми застосували SWOT-аналіз, щоб оцінити діяльність досліджуваних компаній у сфері брендування та маркетингу, виявляючи сильні та слабкі сторони, можливості та загрози. Такий якісний аналіз дозволяє комплексно оцінити брендинг та маркетинг компаній, виявити їхні конкурентні переваги та недоліки, а також врахувати потенційні ризики та перспективи розвитку. Результати. SWOT-аналіз надав можливість оцінити внутрішні та зовнішні чинники, які впливають на конкурентні позиції компаній, а також виявити сильні та слабкі сторони, можливості та загрози для кожної з них. Дослідження показало, що компанії люкс і мас-маркет сегментів використовують різні підходи до брендування та маркетингу, але обидва сегменти активно використовують свої бренди для підвищення конкурентоспроможності. Люксові бренди, такі як Dior та Prada, асоціюються з престижем та елегантністю, а мас-маркет бренди, такі як Nike та Zara, забезпечують доступність своїх товарів для широкого кола споживачів. Основні можливості для всіх брендів включають розширення на нові ринки, розвиток екологічних ініціатив та цифрового маркетингу. Висновки. Усім брендам важливо розвивати нові ринки, екологічні ініціативи та цифровий маркетинг для підвищення конкурентоспроможності. Загрозами для всіх компаній є політичні та військові конфлікти, що призводять до економічних криз, а також репутаційні ризики. Можливостями для обох сегментів є розширення на ринки, що розвиваються, розвиток екологічних ініціатив та етичних практик.

Ключові слова: брендинг, маркетинг, swot-аналіз, транснаціональні корпорації.

The problem statement in a general form and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. The fashion and clothing industry is undergoing

dynamic transformations, driven both by changes in consumer preferences and behavior, and new technological and environmental challenges. The success of Dior, Prada, Zara and Nike on the world stage shows their ability to adapt to rapidly changing market conditions and implement innovative approaches in business strategies. Leading brands are actively implementing digital consumer engagement tools, multi-channel promotion strategies and new operating models. The experience of companies in this area is extremely valuable for understanding future competitive strategies.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The following scientists dealt with the issue of branding research and marketing research in the global market: Stephan Puehringer, Georg Wolfmayr, Carina Altreiter, Claudius Grabner, Ana Rogojanu [1, 3], Nicholas Gane [2], Stefan Arora-Jonsson, Nils Brunsson, Raimund Hasse, Katarina Lagerstrom [4], Porter M. E [5], Gans J. S. [6], Ghemawat P. [7, 8], Zuckerman A. [10], Teece D. J. [11], Kenney M. & Zysman J. [12].

Identification of Unresolved Aspects of the General Problem. However, their works either cover only the theoretical issue of the topic or explore branding and marketing in all markets. So we decided to investigate these issues specifically in the clothing market and even consider certain aspects that distinguish the luxury and mass market segments.

Formulation of the article's objectives. The objective of the article is to conduct a SWOT analysis of the activities of leading companies in the global clothing market in the context of their branding and marketing strategies.

Presentation of the Main Research Material. For a thorough study of the impact of branding and marketing on the competitiveness of multinational companies, we selected four companies in the global clothing market, two of which belong to the mass market (Nike, Zara) and two of which belong to the luxury segment (Dior, Prada). We applied a SWOT analysis to the activities of these companies, focusing on those strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats directly related to the branding and marketing activities of the companies.

This qualitative analysis makes it possible to comprehensively evaluate the branding and marketing of the companies under study, to identify their competitive advantages and disadvantages in this area, as well as to take into account potential risks and prospects for the development of the brand and marketing strategy.

Despite conducting the analysis for each company individually, we will draw conclusions within the segments based on the analyses of the two companies belonging to each segment, as well as across segments, to understand the commonalities and differences between the luxury and mass-market segments in branding and marketing based on the SWOT analysis results. We will start with the first representative of the luxury segment, Dior (table 1).

Table 1 – SWOT analysis of branding and marketing of Dior company

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – a cult and prestigious brand with a history of more than 70 years, associated with sophistication and elegance; – high level of brand awareness and customer loyalty (according to the Interbrand survey, 97% of consumers know about Dior); – strong positioning in the luxury segment, which allows setting high prices; – successful marketing campaigns involving famous models and stars (Jennifer Lawrence, Natalie Portman, Johnny Depp, Nicole Kidman, Rihanna); – high quality of products; – a strong distribution network. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – high prices and positioning in the luxury segment limit the target audience; – dependence on the reputation of LVMH brands (the owner company); – dependence on the reputation of individual designers and creative directors; – limited presence in online sales compared to competitors; – a conservative approach to design, which can repel younger consumers; – use of unethical production practices.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – growing demand for luxury goods in Asia and the Middle East; – expansion of online sales and digital marketing; – collaboration with famous personalities to attract new audiences; – cooperation with other brands; – development of exclusive limited collections; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – fierce competition with other luxury brands (Chanel, Gucci, Louis Vuitton); – currency exchange rate fluctuations affecting prices and sales; – risk of loss of reputation due to scandals or conflicts related to employees, suppliers or product quality; – economic crises, wars and instability

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – development of environmental initiatives and strengthening of environmentally sustainable marketing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> in certain regions, which reduces the demand for luxury items; counterfeits and unlicensed products that can harm the brand image; – the difficulty of maintaining an exclusive image during mass production.
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Source: compiled on the basis of data [14; 23; 27; 40; 41; 42; 43].

Although Prada belongs to the same market segment as Dior, it has somewhat different results in the SWOT analysis (table 2). Despite both being part of the luxury segment, these two companies have different histories, cultural backgrounds, and organizational values. Consequently, their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the global market vary.

Table 2 – SWOT analysis of branding and marketing of Prada company

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – one of the most recognizable luxury brands in the world with high customer loyalty (according to BrandZ, consumer awareness of the brand is 92%); – successful positioning as an avant-garde and fashionable brand thanks to constant innovations in design; – strong retail presence with 634 stores in 70 countries (as of 2021); – successful collaborations and marketing campaigns (Tom Holland, Scarlett Johansson, Benedict Cumberbatch, Emma Watson); – the use of the highest quality materials and careful production control, which guarantees the flawlessness of the products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – a lower level of brand recognition compared to competitors (according to Interbrand, 77%); – too wide a range can blur the brand identity; – relatively low prices in Asia compared to competitors (about 30% of revenue); – inaccessibility in some countries, which may limit growth potential; – slow growth in online sales, small presence in social networks; – dependence on the reputation and management of one family (the founders of Prada); – may be perceived as a brand for the older generation, which may limit its appeal to young people.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – further expansion into the markets of Asia and the Middle East, where the demand for luxury items is growing; – development of online sales, digital marketing and interaction with customers through social networks; – expansion of the product line; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – fierce competition from other luxury brands (LVMH, Kering, Richemont); – currency exchange rate fluctuations and economic instability affecting revenues; – risks of loss of reputation due to conflicts;

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - introduction of more conscious production practices to attract eco-conscious consumers; - cooperation with famous designers and stars to increase brand recognition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - changing consumer preferences due to new trends and popularity of new brands; - damage to reputation and reduced sales due to counterfeiting.
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Source: compiled on the basis of data [24; 43; 44; 45].

Based on the results of the SWOT analysis for the luxury segment companies, it can be concluded that the luxury segment companies have a long brand history and are associated by consumers with prestige, sophistication and elegance; despite the limited segment of consumers due to high prices, the level of recognition of luxury segment companies is high; luxury brands involve world-famous stars in their advertising campaigns, which further fuels the interest in the company among consumers, and especially those who would like to wear the clothes worn by their idol; these companies usually have a small presence in the markets and sell their goods exclusively in their own stores. On the other hand, online sales are not so popular for the company in the luxury segment; since the prices of goods of these brands are much higher, the economic crises in some countries will affect them more strongly. Opportunities for Dior and Prada companies include expansion into the markets of Asia and the Middle East, development of online sales and digital marketing, and sustainable production.

To draw conclusions about the differences in branding and marketing between segments, we also conducted a SWOT analysis for companies in the mass-market segment. Since Zara belongs to a completely different price segment compared to Dior and Prada, its competitive advantages and challenges are likely to differ (table 3).

Table 3 – SWOT analysis of branding and marketing of Zara company

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a recognizable global brand with a presence in 96 countries (more than 2,200 stores); - high speed of response to trends thanks to the "fast fashion" model (new collections twice a month); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the reputation of a "mass brand", which reduces its prestige for some consumers; - dependence on external production and the problem with ethical practices; - limited product differentiation compared to

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – affordable prices that make the brand attractive to a wide audience; – a strong emphasis on online trade and digital marketing (online sales will grow by 25% in 2022); – a powerful strategy for the promotion of environmental initiatives ("Join life" and "Sustainable goals"); – clothing design adapted to different age categories of the population. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> competitors; – vulnerability to fluctuations in demand; – high operating costs.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – expansion of online sales and omnichannel strategy; – investments in sustainable development; – growing demand for inexpensive fashion clothes in developing countries; – increasing the presence in the fast-growing markets of Asia and the Middle East; – expansion of the assortment in related categories; – development of a greater number of environmental initiatives and popularization of conscious production and use. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fierce competition with other brands using the "fast fashion" model (H&M, Forever 21); – reputational risks due to scandals related to violations of labor standards; – increasing the cost of labor and resources in the countries of production; – the negative impact on the environment of the growth of the "fast fashion" trend; – economic instability and changes in consumer preferences.

Source: compiled on the basis of data [14; 25; 32; 33; 34; 35; 43].

A similar SWOT analysis was conducted for another mass-market brand, Nike (table 4). As one of the largest global sports brands, Nike possesses unique competitive advantages and faces specific challenges that differ from those encountered by players in the luxury segment or the «fast fashion» segment.

Table 4 – SWOT analysis of branding and marketing of Nike company

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – one of the most recognizable brands in the world (96% according to Siegel+Gale); – powerful marketing campaigns involving sports stars and other famous people (Michael Jordan, Marcus Rashford, Sky Brown, Cristiano Ronaldo); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – high level of competition with Adidas, Under Armor and other manufacturers of sports goods; – scandals and criticism regarding the use of labor in developing countries; – dependence on suppliers of raw materials and materials; – high costs for marketing and brand

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - leadership in innovations and technologies for sportswear and footwear; - wide presence on the global market (more than 1,100 branded stores); - high consumer loyalty, especially among young people and athletes; - a strong presence in the digital space: the leader among sports brands in terms of the number of followers in social networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> promotion; - dependence on contracts with famous athletes and teams.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - growing demand for sports goods in developing countries; - expanding the range of products for fitness and an active lifestyle; - development of environmental initiatives and production of sustainable products; - access to new market segments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - changes in consumer preferences and transition to competitors; - escalation of trade wars and customs barriers in key markets; - a drop in the purchasing power of consumers due to economic crises; - reputational risks due to labor conflicts and ethical violations.

Source: compiled on the basis of data [14; 26; 36; 45; 46; 47].

Based on the SWOT analysis for mass-market companies, it can be noted that mass-market brands have a strong market presence and their number of stores exceeds 1,000; since companies in this segment offer low to mid-range prices, they are accessible to a broader consumer base, especially appealing to the younger demographic. In addition to their presence in the global market, mass-market brands also exhibit high visibility on social media and well-developed online sales. However, the mass-market segment can be significantly affected by increasing competition among companies, which grows annually due to market expansion. Opportunities for enhancing the competitiveness of Zara and Nike include expanding their product range, entering new markets, and implementing environmental initiatives.

Conclusions. The study of the impact of branding and marketing on competitiveness has shown that luxury and mass-market companies have different approaches and challenges. However, both segments actively leverage their brands to enhance competitiveness. Dior and Prada, as representatives of the luxury

segment, have a strong image and are associated with prestige and elegance. Their advertising campaigns, involving globally renowned celebrities, significantly enhance brand attractiveness. Nonetheless, a limited consumer base due to high prices and dependence on the economic stability of countries are significant challenges. In contrast, Zara and Nike, as representatives of the mass-market segment, demonstrate high accessibility of their products, making them popular among a wide range of consumers. The large number of stores and the development of online sales enable these brands to have a significant market presence. However, high competition in the mass-market segment requires constant product assortment updates and adaptation to new market conditions. To enhance competitiveness, both luxury and mass-market brands can leverage opportunities to expand into new markets, develop environmental initiatives, and digital marketing strategies. Specifically, it is crucial for Dior and Prada to enhance their presence in online sales, while Zara and Nike should focus on introducing innovative products and sustainable solutions. Overall, the results of the study confirmed that branding and marketing play a key role in the competitiveness of companies, regardless of their price segment. It is important to consider the specific strengths and weaknesses of each brand, as well as the opportunities and threats they face in the global market.

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